

Structure tensor-based Gaussian kernel edge-adaptive depth map refinement with triangular point view in images

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ABSTRACT

Image reconstruction is the process of restoring the image resolution. In 3D image reconstruction, the objects in different viewpoints are processed with the triangular point view (TPV) method to estimate object geometry structure for 3D model. This work proposes a depth refinement methodology in preserving the geometric structure of objects using the structure tensor method with a Gaussian filter by transforming a series of 2D input images into a 3D model. The computation of depth map errors can be found by comparing the masked area/patch with the distribution of the original image's greyscale levels using the error pixel-based patch extraction algorithm. The presence of errors in the depth estimation could seriously deteriorate the quality of the 3D effect. The depth maps were iteratively refined based on histogram bins number to improve the accuracy of initial depth maps reconstructed from rigid objects. The existing datasets such as the dataset tanks and unit (DTU) and Middlebury datasets, were used to build the model out of the object scene structure. The results of this work have demonstrated that the proposed patch analysis outperformed the existing state of the art models depth refinement methods in terms of accuracy.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Stereoscopy plays a vital role in computer vision-based systems. Stereo vision involves the process of estimating the 3D models of the scene. Stereo vision employs techniques like triangulation. The process of 3D reconstruction applies triangulation to generate the 3D models from a set of images. The projection of a 3D scene onto a 2D plane leads to some depth loss, as the corresponding image points are constrained to the line of sight from a human's viewpoint. From a single view, the corresponding image points with the line of sight are difficult to match for 3D projection. This problem can be tackled by using multiple images where the correspondence image point can be found by the intersection of two projection rays from the object. This process refers to triangulation, followed to identify the structure or pose of the particular object in the image and the camera calibration.

In the triangulation process, the convolutional neural network (CNN) with multi-view stereo (MVS) [1] based stereo matching approach was predominantly applied. Multiple 2D images can be converted into 3D models by exploiting the extrinsic and intrinsic camera parameters. Chang and Ho [2] proposed the depth

determination of contours from the image point coordination between pairs of images. Moreover, they have mentioned that the correspondence problem of finding the matched images can be triangulated in 3D space.

The measure of disparity would be used to identify the structure or pose of a particular object. The measure of disparity can be used to predict the object distance from the camera viewpoint. The item closest to the camera is the one closest in depth. Khalil *et al.* [3] proposed a disparity measure based depth map estimation. The value of the left and right pictures was used to calculate the depth map for the stereo images at the correspondence point pixel. They have augmented the depth map depending on the structural magnitude of the 3D model. The lesser the disparity value, the greater the object's depth. Owing to this fact, the generated adaptive object structure has produced convincing visual quality.

The state-of-the-art models have shown better precision in depth estimation and refinement. The stereo matching and MVS vision techniques needs to be exploited to recognize objects in patches over the images. The following, section 2 describes the related works. The methods to calculate the camera parameters are discussed in section 3. The point-matching algorithm for determining the defect using the pixel-wise calculation for both the left and right images is discussed in section 4. Finally, section 5 concludes the work.

2. RELATED WORK

This section discusses the various approaches to handle image reconstruction with stereo matching and multi-view stereo network (MVSNet) using similarity metrics. Scharstein and Szeliski [4] reviewed that the stereo unification/match algorithm usually consists of steps, such as matching of cost calculation, matching of aggregation cost, disparity value calculation, and disparity enhancement. Aggregation of match costs with the neighborhood pixel points for local or specific methods [5]–[7] would choose the optimal disparity based on the winner-take-all strategy. Global or generic methods proposed in [8], [9] depicted that the energy function could be used to minimize the optimal disparity.

According to Huang *et al.* [10], a semi-global matching algorithm was designed for the approximation of optimizing global methods with dynamic programming. Kendall *et al.* [11], the regression of disparity maps obtained from the stereo pair matching and learning of geometric structure by the deep stereo network was done with MVS. Zhang *et al.* [12] the contextual information from the cost volume was learned using 3D convolutions using end-to-end architecture. MVSNet [13] and pyramid stereo matching network (PSMNet) [14] represented the underlying/base networks for demonstrating the cascade cost volume applications in stereo matching tasks. In the context of CNN based networks, the similarity measure of small patch images was used in stereo matching methods with softmax argmin operation to provide better matching results for 3D cost volume in stereo [15]. The 3D cost volume can boost the overall performance. However, they are less prone to down-sampled cost volumes, and to generate high-resolution disparity images, they rely on interpolation [16] operations. The most availed method in 3D is the cost volume, first introduced by the global context network (GCNet) [8] for stereo vision, which uses the regression technique for finding the best match results with the identification of the intensity range of masked and unmasked regions using softargmin operation.

The cascade cost volume proposed by Gu *et al.* [17] demonstrated a method for MVS stereo and stereo matching and compared their results with the learning-based approaches for accuracy and less memory usage. This method has used homography warping with CNN for hypothesis depth estimation using feature pyramids utilizing the low-level features with the downsampling technique. In the areas of ill-posed occurrences, which are mainly caused by repeated patterns, occluded regions, texture-less regions, and reflexive planes, the cost of estimating the pixel-wise is generally ambiguous. To overcome this issue, cost volume-based 3D CNN at multiple scales was used to aggregate the contextual information of the images. This approach has resulted with regularized noise-contamination with high cost.

MVS has higher accuracy in comparison with stereo matching and structure from motion [18]. The MVS technique, based on cost volume, estimates the relationship between the surface and the voxel. Then, the 3D point cloud-based method considers 3D points for iterative processing and regression. Depth map reconstruction finds the depth map and estimation using the reference image and a few source images. Greene and Roy [19] attenuation aware MVS was designed to improve the matching confidence of volume using pixel-wise contextual information of extracted features from the local scenes and regularizing the confidence pair volume with multi-level ray fusion modules.

Recurrent MVSNet [20] was one of the methods used in the MVSNet for object recognition using recurrent neural networks, which aids in reducing the computational cost by regularizing the 2D cost maps using gated recurrent unit (GRU) following the depth direction for better prediction. Structural orientation is essential to elevate the image quality. The enhancement of structural magnitude and orientation also plays a vital role in the field of 3D imaging application. The geometric structure of the objects could be easily

deteriorated with the presence of noises/blurriness and occlusions in the image. So the edge adaptive mechanisms of metrics such as structural similarity index measure (SSIM), which is superior to mean squared error, signal to noise ratio, peak signal noise ratio are failed to concentrate on the textured regions [21]. The image quality prediction in accumulated error areas reveals less structural information for building a 3D model. The drawback of the structure tensor-based edge adaptive method was analyzed and the gap in studies were identified. In the proposed approach the structure tensor with Gaussian kernel was applied in attaining the geometric structure information. The proposed approach is expected to overcome the drawbacks of the coarse depth maps obtained from traditional methods with increased resolution.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Stereo network is the process of creating 3D images from a given set of 2D images taken in multiple sets or 2 views concerning the camera parameters. The stereo camera positions are similar to human eye vision in determining objects with the left and right eye simultaneously. The input images from the stereo vision were preprocessed so as to remove the barrel and tangential distortion. The projection matching with the image rectification was done after confirming that the images were paired with their respective plane coordinates. Then, the measures of pixel shifts were used to calculate the disparity map. The Algorithm 1 for the triangulation point view with stereoNet-based disparity calculation is discussed. The K-nearest neighbor (KNN) based distance metric was used to determine the distance between the nearby pixels for generating depth maps based on the camera parameters.

Algorithm 1: Triangulation point view in MVS

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Input: Set of images with labeled data
         image orientations and resolutions
         depth map construction, d is the disparity value
output: depth map enhancement
          depth map estimation
while depth map unification do
  if d is similar to K-neighboring views, then
    if pixel label = class of interest, then
      keep d;
      project point in X 3D;
    else
      discard;
    end
  else
    discard;
  end
end

```

3.1. Network architecture for triangulation in stereo networks

Triangulation point view is the method for determining images in a triangle viewpoint for robustly identifying the scene's structure. The convolutional neural net structure extracts the features of the input images, and the correspondence matching describes those features among the image pixel-wise for both the left and right stereo images in a triangulation convergence for understanding the scene structure. Multi-view triangulation methods [22] suffer from high computational costs. So robust triangulation was proposed to tackle this problem. The geometric verification was done to find the image matching, and the mismatch will lead to an adjustment in the rectification of the object geometry structure for coordinating the camera calibration using the structure tensor method [23].

The pixel-wise matching in both the left and right images is shown in Figure 1(a) with the triangular point view (TPV) for matching the image coordinate concerning the world coordinate system. The pixel a in the left image is considered to find the similarity between the pixel from the right image a' that is if the pixel values a and a' are similar or not is seen by the pixel matching algorithm [24], which is discussed. Figure 1(b) describes the point projection in a MVSNet with a triangulation point view for the predictions from coarse to fine-tuning parameters through CNN and the point flow module. The point flow is one of the methods used to determine the projection of point flows from the camera parameters for obtaining the point cloud as the data representation. The TPV method was used to refine coarse depth prediction to achieve a better refinement strategy using 3D CNN regression.

Figure 1. Stereo image pair patch selection, (a) for pixel-wise matching in stereo-based images and (b) projection of return on investment (ROI) in triangulation viewpoint

3.2. Depth refinement methodology

To triangulate the scene, the correspondence search in the given set of images was performed with the overlapped regions and the projections of the same points were found. The features were detected as invariant to any geometric changes; feature matching was also done to provide the output as the correspondence feature pair for linearity. This technique suits well for the smaller sets of images, which are less error-prone than the more extensive set of images. Figure 2 describes the structure comparison before and after the refinement of depth maps.

The point matching finds the difference of given images by the following sum of absolute difference (SAD) metric or SSIM; usually, in the 3D reconstruction model, the representation of multiple 2D images in the form as $I = \{I_1, I_2, \dots, I_n\}$ and the corresponding matching of the pixels of the input image was done using the stereo matching technique with the TPV-based images from the camera viewpoint are denoted as $I_i = match(x1, t1)$ where the x1 represents the pixel value of the input image into consideration. Moreover, the t1 is the template pixel or ground truth value for the matching image. The matching of images was done either by template match or the pixel-wise match (Algorithm 2).

Algorithm 2: For pixel matching and finding deterioration among images

Input: Coarse Depth Map

Output: Refined Depth Map

Read the input RGB stereo image.

Calculate disparity 'dis'

Set numdisparities=64 and block size=11 based on resolution

Calculate SSIM for original and dis image
If SSIM value > reference image
 Perform depth refinement
 For each block, the Gaussian kernel sigma=0.2
 Obtain edge adaptive object structure for 'dis' images
Else
 Obtain the patch and refine using an average based filter
 Repeat steps from 3 to 7 for each pixel in the images
End
 Result: refined depth map.

Figure 2. Geometric invariants correction with depth refinement module using structure tensor

3.2.1. Depth calculation and refinement of depth maps

For the reconstruction of the object image, the depth image has to be determined. The computation of depth image using $Z = (f \times d)/(x_r - x_l)$ parameters of the above expression are detailed as f is camera focal length concerning object, d is measure of distance between two cameras in focus, z is depth of the image, x_r is right image pixel position, and x_l is left image pixel position. Pixel mismatch identified through the histogram calculation by following the steps such as:

- a. Count the number of pixels in both left and right images for the intensity k

$$\text{Count}(I_L(x, y) = k) = \text{His}_l(k)$$

$$\text{Count}(I_R(x, y) = k) = \text{His}_r(k)$$

- b. Calculate the normalized histograms for stereo image along with the dimensions of respective images

$$\text{Nor}_l(k) = \text{Hist}_l(k)/(m * n)$$

$$\text{Nor}_r(k) = \text{Hist}_r(k)/(m * n)$$

- c. The absolute difference between the normalized histograms of both images

$$\text{Absdif}(k) = |\text{Nor}_l(k) - \text{Nor}_r(k)|$$

- d. Calculate SAD between the normalized histograms

$$SAD_{normhist} = \text{sum}(Absdif(k))$$

where $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, L - 1$ where L is the maximum intensity level (usually 256 for 8-bit images).

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In the proposed work, the DTU and the Middlebury datasets were used [25] for evaluating the triangulation and pyramidal structure in this MVSNet. These datasets contain images taken under different lighting conditions covering 124 scenes examined in 7 different lighting conditions at 49 or 64 view directions. Then, the real-world scene correspondence with small-depth scale images taken from the Tanks and Temple dataset [26], contains realistic scenes with small depth ranges. These training sets were evaluated with TPV method and compared with several MVSNet structures such as FastMVS (extracts features before projecting onto plane), DeepMVS and PyramidMVS.

4.1. Implementation

The accuracy and completeness measures of the DTU datasets were computed for the scenes exposed under different lighting conditions. The input taken from the DTU dataset was fed into the prediction pattern of CNN to identify the dissimilarity measure among the different sets of inputs for object recognition. The training image, taken from the MVS strategy, was analyzed with the state of the models for comparative results. Figure 3(a) to Figure 3(d) describes the intensity variation result and disparity image for the provided inputs using the subtraction method and distance measurement of pixel match, respectively. The input ill-posed images, such as those that underwent different lighting, texture, and occlusions considered for reconstruction, are done via different model architectures.

Figure 4(a) to Figure 4(d) describes the processing of stereo images by the edge adaptive structure method in obtaining the fine depth map from the coarse depth map. The depth map was enhanced using kernel parameter with $\sigma=0.2$. The edge adaptive kernel based on the blocksize was chosen to get a refined depth map for better visualization quality in a 3D model.

Figure 3. Stereo imaging correspondence pixel coordination (a) Left Image (b) Right Image, (c) initial depth map, and (d) disparity map without pixel matching

Figure 4. Structure preserving smoothness a) disparity map with distance pixel measurement using color, (b) coarse depth map, (c) edge adaptive kernel-based structure tensor method for predicting geometric structure of objects visibility in construction of 3D model, and (d) final refined depth maps.

Table 1 describes the similarity measure from the input stereo images with rectification and without rectification values. The value of SSIM rectified stereo images is nearer to the max value, and the accuracy of final depth map compared with initial depth maps is higher. Refining depth maps using the structure tensor method with Gaussian kernel obtains the refined depth map with better accuracy. Table 2 describes the quantitative measure of TPV with histogram patch matching is compared with the algorithm grab-cut and Traditional histogram for analyzing the pixel probability distribution range. The ranges are decided based on the bin selected for various objects in the image. The precision results of the images are evaluated using metrics such as the mean absolute elevation error and root mean square error (RMSE). The edge adaptive structure tensor method using TPV in correspondence pixel match achieves higher accuracy than other models using grab-cut optimization parameters. The lesser mean absolute error value in pixel matching reduces the complexity of the deteriorate effect in the selective patch.

Table 1. Similarity metric for rectified and unrectified images

Image	MAE	RMSE	SSIM	Structure tensor similarity measure
Unrectified stereo images	5864.73	76.5	0.407,0.415	17.014
Rectified stereo images	1292.95	35.9	0.544,0.607	10.448

Table 2. The RMSE and mean elevation error (pixels)

Algorithms	Masked region		UnMasked region	
	RMSE	Mean absolute elevation error	RMSE	Mean absolute elevation error
Grab-cut method	0.117	0.326	0.119	0.371
Traditional histogram	0.806	0.114	0.128	0.602
TPV method +histogram patch matching	0.108	0.136	0.052	0.214

4.2. Stereo matching

This section uses the histogram analysis method to describe the datasets used for stereo-matching images in creating disparity maps for the respective problem. The histogram calculation for the given images uses the OpenCV histogram method, which takes a positional argument as the input image, channels, mask, intensity values, and pixel value for every pixel. The mask was chosen based on the user's decision to select the region on which the algorithm has to work/depend for pixel matching. The class intervals are calculated based on the data points in the image. Figure 5 shows how the mask is chosen for the particular patch to identify the occluded or mismatched pixel region. The masked histogram can show the pixel deformity and aid smoothing using filters. The results shown in Figure 5 are taken from Middlebury dataset.

Figure 5. Image histogram for the mask and unmask region

Mask region suggested using the number of bins in a color histogram to represent the distance between classes. Histograms of good quality require patches with sufficiently large numbers of sample pixels. A non-contextual edge detector such as the conventional Canny operator produces strong responses to texture areas when textures and object sizes are comparable. Object contours may be obscured in the final product of such an operator. Compare the colors of masked and unmasked patches of images for precision evaluation with traditional methods. Figure 6 demonstrates how accuracy is achieved with the different methods in the iterative refinement of depth maps concerning iterations. The depth map is refined to correct the boundaries and check the misalignment between the red, green, blue (RGB) image and the depth map.

Figure 6. Number of Iterations for achieving accuracy using different methods

5. CONCLUSION

Hence a novel TPV-based object texture identification was proposed. We have analyzed the efficiency of the proposed algorithm under different lighting conditions using the SAD method. The determination of pixel-wise similarity matching was done using the pixel match algorithm for both the left and right images and they were analysed with the other metrics such as SSIM and mean square error. The TPV method, along with the camera parameter, serves as the input for pixel matching and the depth maps were found to process the input image for better perception of the scene. The histogram of images determines the pixel intensity variations due to occlusion or discontinuities in the disparity map. This identification has led the system to deal with the problem caused by object occlusion in stereo images. As a future enhancement utilization of super-pixels in the patch-based method will be tested instead of taking all patches of an image in a holistic manner.

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